

Soil and crop management

Effect of different methods and time of threshing on IR6 grain losses

C. A. Khuhro, I. M. Bhatti, and M. H. Balock, Rice Research Institute, Dokri, Sind, Pakistan

Threshing is a source of substantial postharvest grain losses. Traditional threshing in Sind Province, Pakistan, is by animal trampling after paddy has been stacked for as long as 1-2 mo. This method leads to large grain losses and grain quality deterioration.

We studied the effect of different methods and time of threshing on grain losses at three locations. Hand, bullock, and mechanical threshing were tested at 4 d and 3, 6, and 9 wk after harvest, using grain at the top, middle, and bottom of the stacks (see table).

Analysis of individual threshing methods for different times of stacking in different portions showed that hand threshing and mechanical threshing

Effect of threshing methods and timing on total grain loss, ^a Sind, Pakistan.

Threshing method	Total grain loss ^b (%)					
	Top of stack		Middle of stack		Bottom of stack	
	<i>4 d after harvest</i>					
Hand	0.27	e	0.26	e	0.28	e
Bullock	4.23	de	4.00	de	4.37	de
Mechanical	0.55	e	0.55	de	0.56	e
	<i>3 wk</i>					
Hand	0.34	e	0.43	e	0.44	e
Bullock	5.54	cde	8.2	de	12.87	ab
Mechanical	0.40	e	0.50	e	0.64	e
	<i>6 wk</i>					
Hand	0.32	e	0.56	e	0.50	e
Bullock	4.95	de	4.11	de	13.06	ab
Mechanical	0.72	e	0.66	e	0.58	e
	<i>9 wk</i>					
Hand	0.27	e	0.51	e	0.60	e
Bullock	10.89	ab	4.04	bcd	16.09	a
Mechanical	0.92	e	0.97	e	0.73	e

^a Means of 3 replications at 3 locations. ^b Separation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

produced minimum grain losses. However, with bullock threshing, grain losses increased when threshing was delayed. The bottom portion of the

stack was most seriously affected. Those losses can be minimized to 4% if bullock threshing is not delayed beyond 4 d after harvest. □

Effect of organic and inorganic manuring on rice nurseries

M. S. Maskina, O. P. Meelu, and P. S. Sandhu, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

A combination of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers can improve the root environment and release of nutrients to rice nurseries.

We studied the effect of using a combination of organic and inorganic nitrogen on the rice nursery at PAU farm in 1981 and 1982. Soil was a loamy sand (Ustochrept) with pH 8.4, low organic carbon (0.23%), and 87-8-86 kg available NPK/ha.

N was applied at 0, 60, and 120 kg/ha. Farmyard manure, poultry manure, and azolla were applied at 15, 4, and 10 t/ha. In one treatment, dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata* was raised for 1 mo and incorporated as green manure 3 d before sowing the rice nursery. Dhaincha fresh

weight was 8 to 10 t/ha. Organic manures and 10 kg P/ha were applied before last puddling. Nitrogen was applied in equal splits at sowing and at 15 and 30 d after sowing. Nurseries were in 10- × 2-m² beds and planted with 1 kg seed. Beds were sown the last week of May and data were recorded 45 d later.

Green manure combined with 60 kg N/ha produced nursery plant biomass equal to that with 120 kg N/ha (see table). Height, color, and leaves of nursery plants were affected favorably by the application of green manure and poultry manure. Seedling strength (see table) was determined as dry matter per unit height

$$\left(\frac{\text{dry matter of the plant (mg)}}{\text{ht of the plant (cm)}} \right)$$

and was highest in the green manure treatment.

Uptake of essential macro- and micro-nutrients improved with application of organic manures (see figure). Uptake of

Effect of organic manures on uptake of essential nutrients by nursery plants (mean 1981-82), Ludhiana, India.

Effect of organic and inorganic nitrogen on growth of nursery (mean of 1981 and 1982), Ludhiana, India.

Treatment		Dry matter (mg/plant)	Leaves/plant	Plant ht (cm)	Color index ^a (A)	Seedling strength (mg/cm) (B)	Seedling quality (A × B)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N (kg/ha)	Organic N							
0	–	76	6	18	1	4	4	–
60	–	152	8	25	2	6	12	5.6
120	–	212	9	30	3	7	22	6.6
60	Farmyard manure	153	8	27	2	6	11	5.5
60	Poultry manure	169	8	32	3	5	16	–
60	Green manure	215	8	28	3	8	24	6.5
60	Azolla	174	7	26	2	7	14	–

^a1 = pale yellow, 3 = dark green.

N, P, K, S, Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu in treatments receiving 60 kg N/ha and dhaincha green manure was higher than with 60 kg N alone and equaled that of 120 kg N. Nursery treatments that received 120 kg N/ha and green manure + 60 kg N/ha yielded significantly more grain than other treatments (see table). □

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Influence of phosphorus and pyrite on azolla growth

S. Venkataraman and S. Kannaiyan, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the effect of superphosphate (SSP), Mussorie rock phosphate (MRP), and pyrite on azolla growth in pot culture. Treatments were SSP alone, MRP alone, SSP and pyrite, MRP and pyrite, at 0, 5, 10, 15, and 20 kg P/ha. Azolla at 200 g/m² was inoculated and 20 ppm carbofuran was applied. Azolla

Influence of phosphorus (P), Mussorie rock phosphate (MRP) and pyrite on azolla growth, Tamil Nadu, India.

P (kg/ha)	SSP		SSP + pyrite		MRP		MRP' + pyrite	
	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control
Control (0)	90.0	–	111	–	101	–	100	–
5	129.0	43	138	24	108	6	133	32
10	142.0	58	146	31	114	13	141	41
15	151.5	68	157	41	120	19	153	52
20	166.0	84	177	59	120	19	159	59
LSD (P = 0.05)		LSD: 6.284		LSD: 8.019		LSD: 8.010		LSD: 5.824

fresh weight was recorded 10 d after inoculation.

All P treatments increased azolla

growth over that of the control (see table). Results indicate that MRP + pyrite is superior for azolla growth. □

Azolla as a substitute for fertilizer

N. Haq, and D. Rosh, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Mingora (Swat); and P. Shah, NWFP Agricultural University, Peshawar, Pakistan

We sought to determine how much N fertilizer can be saved by growing azolla, using J.P.5 rice at ARS in Mingora in 1982. The station is at 35°N latitude and at 975 m altitude. Climate is cool and irrigation water is 15°C.

Azolla treatments, similar to those adopted for 1981-82 INSFFER trials (see table), were in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications in 5- × 3-m plots. Plant height, tillers/hill, and grain yield were recorded and statistically analyzed.

Yield with azolla culture was similar to that with 60 kg applied N/ha (see table). We found that azolla culture has a

Rice yield and other data from azolla experiments at ARS, Mingora (Swat), Peshawar, Pakistan.

Treatment (N/ha)	Panicles/hill	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0 N, 0 azolla, 20- × 20-cm spacing	6	98	3.2
60 kg N, 20- × 20-cm spacing	7	98	3.7
60 kg N, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	105	4.8
Azolla incorporation before transplanting, 30 kg N, 20- × 20-cm spacing	8	100	3.8
Azolla incorporation before transplanting, 30 kg N, 40- × 10-cm spacing	9	110	5.0
Azolla grown once before and once after transplanting and incorporated, 20- × 20-cm spacing	6	100	4.1
Azolla grown once before and once after transplanting and incorporated, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	101	4.5
Azolla grown twice after transplanting, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	101	4.7
90 kg N as urea in 3 splits, 0 azolla, 20- × 20-cm spacing	9	105	4.7
90 kg N as urea in 3 splits, 0 azolla, 40- × 10-cm spacing	9	105	5.5

beneficial effect on soil structure, soil microflora, and micronutrient availability. The azolla effect may persist longer than

N fertilizers on subsequent crops and its effect may increase over time to surpass those of commercial N fertilizers. □